

Bioengineering Enhanced Antioxidant Systems in Transgenic Plants - Strategies, Outcomes, and Challenges: A Review

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ABSTRACT

*Reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide radicals, hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals are continuously synthesized in plants and can cause adverse effects when coupled with abiotic stress. Such stresses include salinity, cold environment, UV radiation, and more. Excess production of ROS can cause adverse effects like lipid peroxidation, increase in protein denaturation, membrane damage, and impaired photosynthesis. To solve such an issue, plants rely on a coordinated antioxidant network consisting of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant components. The progress in plant genetic engineering has enabled targeted enhancement of these antioxidant systems which in turn improves stress tolerance and productivity. Strategies such as overexpression of individual antioxidant enzymes, organelle-targeted expression, multi-gene stacking within pathways like the AsA-GSH cycle and metabolic engineering of non-enzymatic antioxidants have introduced new methods of protecting plants from deleterious ROS species. Cases studied include transgenic *Nicotiana tabacum*, *Solanum lycopersicum*, and other species. These cases tell us the substantial improvements in detoxification of ROS in affected plants by getting results that include reduction in lipid peroxidation and stabilized photosynthetic performance under abiotic stress. Despite this, however, several challenges remain in balancing ROS homeostasis, optimizing promoter choice, avoiding metabolic bottlenecks and even managing gene-dosage effects. This review talks about strategies, outcomes and challenges that you can face when bioengineering enhanced antioxidant systems in transgenic plants.*

Keywords: *Transgenic plants, antioxidants, ROS, oxidative damage, bioengineering, photosynthesis*

I. INTRODUCTION

Plants produce reactive oxygen species like peroxidases, super-oxides, and hydroxyl radicals during normal metabolism. These levels increase rapidly under abiotic conditions like low temperature, salinity, or UV radiation which in turn causes harmful effects like increase in protein denaturation, lipid peroxidation and DNA damage[1,2]. This type of damage can impair growth, and reduce photosynthetic efficiency of the plant. To mitigate oxidative stress and its deleterious

effects, plants have evolved a system of defense against it. This multilayered defense system includes low-molecular weight scavengers or antioxidant molecules (like ascorbate, glutathione, tocopherols, and phenolics), and a suite of enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), Ascorbate peroxidases (APX), Dehydroascorbate reductase (DHAR), Peroxidase (POD) which seek out Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) and detoxify them into lesser reactive forms [2,3]. Enzymes like SOD convert superoxides by dismutation into peroxides, which in turn get changed to water by CAT and APX by the ascorbate-glutathione cycle. To increase yield and productivity, especially in agricultural fields, it becomes important to genetically engineer affected plants express or enhance these defense systems in order to combat reactive oxygen species. Many plants which were affected with superoxides causing oxidative stress were genetically engineered to have an enhanced system of enzymes like SOD, CAT and peroxidases, which could convert such substrates into non-reactive forms. Genetically engineered plants showed higher tolerance and productivity than affected individuals in abiotic conditions, primarily low temperature, high salinity, and UV radiation. [4].

II. A FEW EXAMPLES OF TRANSGENIC PLANTS EXPRESSING ANTIOXIDANT GENES

II.I. Ascorbate Peroxidase (APX) gene

In *Nicotiana tabacum*, the cytosolic ascorbate peroxidase (APX) enzyme plays a central role in detoxifying higher levels of Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), generated during various abiotic stresses such as UV radiation. According to a study done by Saurabh C. Saxena, et al. (2011), pea-derived APX gene (apx1) was introduced to *Nicotiana tabacum*, which when administered, showed a 2.3-fold increase in cytosolic APX production in these transgenic tobacco plants. With this, they were able to observe a decrease in ROS levels triggered by oxidative stress. Although hydrogen peroxide and MDA markers show that there is less oxidative damage, proline levels (another indicator) show a slight increase in the body of the plants. This is because even though higher proline levels could indicate higher abiotic stress, it could also indicate that the plant is actively upregulating its osmoprotective and antioxidant systems as a presumptive defence, separating it from being a potential sign of distress. In the leaves, however, Ascorbate levels were significantly lower in transgenic plants than in the wild type varieties. This was because of increased UV exposure in leaves, led to a higher concentration and accumulation of hydrogen peroxide. However, it was reported that after four hours, these transgenic plants accumulated 62% less hydrogen peroxide than the wild type. This indicates an overall significant decrease in ROS species even if ascorbate levels themselves aren't increasing as much [2].

II.II Glutathione peroxidase (GPX) gene

Glutathione peroxidase (GPX) is another antioxidant that helps in removing harmful ROS like H_2O_2 . When the GPX gene from the green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* was introduced

into tobacco plants, GPX activity increased in these transgenic plants. Because of this, the plants were able to control ROS levels better which reduced cellular damage. These transgenic plants showed lower Lipid peroxidation, thereby, lesser membrane damage. This indicates that their antioxidant defence became stronger and their cell membranes were better protected during stress. Under stressful conditions, these plants continued to grow normally while wild type plants showed more stress effects. This improvement was mainly seen due to the higher strength of the antioxidant system, not necessarily because of any change in growth pattern or metal absorption. Such results show that higher GPX levels helped *Nicotiana tabacum* survive better in harsh conditions by lowering oxidative damage and protecting important cellular functions. [5]

II. III Glutathione Transferase (TvGST) gene

Heavy metal contamination is an extremely prevalent environmental crisis around the world, constantly disrupting soil ecosystems, causing a decrease in soil fertility and crop productivity [6]. Abiotic stress is not only limited to UV, draught etc but also includes presence of heavy metals in soil. This includes exposure to heavy metals like cadmium, which are extremely perilous to plants. In a study done by Prachy Dixit et al. (2011), a glutathione transferase gene, TvGST, from *Trichoderma virens* was introduced into *Nicotiana tabacum* using *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation to improve cadmium tolerance. The presence of the gene in transgenic plants was confirmed through southern blot and RT-PCR. Under cadmium stress, the plants expressing TvGST showed improved tolerance compared to non-transgenic/normal wildtype varieties. Lower lipid peroxidation levels and higher activity of antioxidants were observed. Such results show that the transgenic plants could detoxify ROS more efficiently while suffering minimal oxidative damage. Even though the transgenic plants were more tolerant, the amount of cadmium accumulated in them was observed to be almost the same or even slightly less than compared to wild varieties. This shows that TvGST can help develop crops that are tolerant to cadmium, while also inhibiting excess absorption of the metal, which is important to keep heavy metals strictly out of the food chain[7]. This effectively proves that antioxidant enzymes play a very important role in stress tolerance.

II.IV. Iron Superoxide Dismutase 1 (FeSOD1)

The expression of *Arabidopsis thaliana* FeSOD1 (Iron Superoxide Dismutase 1) in the chloroplasts of tomato showed improved antioxidant capacity at specific sites, stabilizing photosynthesis, protecting plants from oxidative stress. The FeSOD1 coding region was attached to a transit peptide and introduced with *Agrobacterium*. Such an action increased chloroplastic SOD activity by about 40-185% in tomato. Improvements led to greater resilience to UV-mediated oxidative stress, primarily UV-A stress. This was evident through higher oxygen evolution rates, better PSII stability, less lipid peroxidation, and smaller declines in delayed fluorescence compared to wild varieties. Although there were some ultrastructural changes, like expanded plastoglobuli and altered starch distribution, these did not indicate any truly negative

effects[4]. Overall, this experiment done by E.N. Baranova et al. (2011), demonstrates that strengthening is a key antioxidant step inside the organelle, where reactive oxygen species are produced, can significantly reduce oxidative damage and maintain photosynthetic function.

II.V. Overexpression of single antioxidant enzyme genes

Introduction of genes that encode for scavengers like SOD, APX, CAT, GST, and GR have been shown to consistently enhance enzyme activity in transgenic plants. Overexpression of Cu/ZnSOD (Copper/Zinc superoxide dismutase) in *Solanum tuberosum* (potato) resulted in a 1.38-fold increase in SOD activity compared to wild varieties. [1]. Similarly, FeSOD1 gene being overexpressed in plants like *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) and *Nicotiana tabacum* (Tobacco) from *Arabidopsis thaliana* showed 40-185% increase in SOD activity. [4]. The introduction of MnSOD gene under the control of CaMV 35S promoter led to more than a two-fold increase in MnSOD activity in transgenic plants when compared to its wild varieties. When these transgenic plants were exposed to 150 mM of sodium chloride, much lower levels of malondialdehyde (a biomarker for lipid peroxidation), were observed. Because of this, transgenic plants were able to survive in highly saline conditions without suffering oxidative stress[8]. In *Solanum tuberosum*, the gene StSOD1 for Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase was overexpressed, and the transgenic lines possessing it had a 1.38-fold increase in SOD activity. In colder conditions that could most definitely cause stress to the plants (i.e. 4°C for 48 hours), transgenic plants showed increased enzymatic activity for catalases and peroxidases. To confirm, the experiment done showed lower levels of malondialdehyde (MDA). [5]

Under salt stress, plants commonly suppress the expression of key cell cycle regulators. This down regulation inhibits cell division, ultimately limiting growth of the plant. This also affects root development and overall biomass accumulation declines. This in turn affects the plant's capacity for water and nutrient uptake. The resulting limitations exacerbate stress severity, giving rise to secondary effects such as osmotic balance, nutrient deficiency, ion toxicity... etc. [9] One example of overcoming this is overexpression of DHAR or MDHAR in transgenic tobacco, which showed higher levels of ASH (reduced ascorbate) and better tolerance against salt and osmotic stress [10].

Overexpression of Mn-SOD in transgenic *Arabidopsis*, *L. esculentum*, and tobacco showed enhanced tolerance against salt stress. Overexpression of Cu/Zn-SOD from a mangrove (*Avicennia marina*) in transgenic rice was more tolerant to 150 mM NaCl stress. Overexpression of glutathione peroxidase (AcGPx2) in *Arabidopsis* has been shown to enhance tolerance to oxidative damage induced by multiple abiotic stresses, including salinity. Similarly, chloroplast-targeted overexpression of ascorbate peroxidase (APX) in *Nicotiana tabacum* improved salt tolerance. [11] Simultaneous expression of three antioxidant enzymes Cu/Zn-SOD, APx, and DHAR in transgenic tobacco increased DHAR activity by 1.6-2.1 times, and high ratio of reduced ascorbate to DHA and GSSH to reduced GSH in chloroplasts enabling plants with enhanced tolerance to

multiple environmental stresses. Transgenic *Arabidopsis* with transcription factor YAP1 from yeast showed increased activities of antioxidant enzymes like SOD, CAT, APX, GST, and GR under various NaCl concentrations.

III.II Organelle-targeted expression

Organelle-specific gene transfer can be effectively achieved using organelle-targeting peptides. For instance, chloroplast-targeting peptides have been employed to deliver FeSOD1 enzymes into plastids, enabling the production of iron-dependent superoxide dismutase within the chloroplast. This precise targeting helps protect the photosynthetic machinery from harmful oxidative stress and cellular damage [4]. In another example, exogenous application of ascorbic acid and glutathione strengthened chloroplast antioxidant defences under salt stress by enhancing SOD, APX, and GR activities, increasing endogenous redox pools, and reducing H₂O₂ and lipid peroxidation. These protective effects were more pronounced in the salt-tolerant cultivar Pokkali, with glutathione exerting a stronger influence on plastidial ROS scavenging. [12]

III.III Co-expression / Gene-stacking

Unlike introducing singular enzymes or overexpression of singular enzymes, co-expression relies on introduction of multiple enzymes to a plant variety, usually enzymes that work in the same redox pathway. This includes examples like the Ascorbate-Glutathione cycle (AsA-GSH) (Fig.1).[13]. In such a cycle, enzymes like SOD, APX, GR, MDHAR, and DHAR are co-expressed as they are required to detoxify ROS species, especially H₂O₂. CAD plants (Cu/Zn-SOD, APX, DHAR plants) are introduced with these three genes. Cu/Zn-SOD acts by converting superoxide radicals to hydrogen peroxide, which would be later taken up by APX to produce water using ascorbate. DHAR regenerates ascorbate from its oxidised form, DHA. A 1.62.0-fold increase can be observed under such a co-expression in transgenic plants. [14].

Figure 1: Ascorbate-Glutathione (AsA-GSH) cycle (GR, glutathione reductase; GSH, glutathione; DHAR, dehydroascorbate reductase; GSSR, oxidized glutathione; AsA, ascorbate; DHA, dehydroascorbate; MDHA, monodehydroascorbate; MDHAR, monodehydroascorbate reductase.)

III.IV. Metabolic engineering of non enzymatic antioxidants

γ tocopherol methyltransferase is an enzyme known to synthesize vitamin-E. It particularly converts γ -tocopherol into α -tocopherol, known to be a very strong antioxidant. This means, when γ -TMT is overexpressed or even administered at a certain level, it can combat against ROS species just as good as enzymatic scavengers like SOD, APX, CAT...etc. This method was used in the plant *Perilla frutescens*, where it was overexpressed. Due to this, there was a near three-fold reduction of DPPH IC₅₀ (an indicator for ROS species in assays to measure antioxidant strength) when tests were run. Lower DPPH IC₅₀ levels indicates a stronger presence of antioxidants like α -tocopherol. Similar strategies target ascorbate biosynthesis or glutathione synthesis to enlarge the AsA GSH pool. [3].

IV. LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES OF ANTIOXIDANT BIOENGINEERING

IV.I Balancing ROS pathways

In plant cells, certain enzymes may be highly sensitive to the products generated by other metabolic reactions. When harmful intermediates are not efficiently converted into less toxic compounds by associated enzymes, oxidative damage can persist. A well-known example is Cu/

Zn-superoxide dismutase (Cu/Zn-SOD), which is susceptible to inhibition by hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), the very product formed during the conversion of superoxide radicals (O_2^-). If hydrogen peroxide is not subsequently detoxified by downstream antioxidant enzymes such as peroxidases or catalases, oxidative stress continues because the activity of Cu/Zn-SOD becomes impaired. [14]

This limitation highlights an important challenge in enzyme co-expression strategies, as such interactions may influence experimental outcomes and lead to unintended effects. However, studies by Young Pyo-Lee and colleagues demonstrated that co-expression of superoxide dismutase with antioxidant enzymes such as ascorbate peroxidase (APX) or dehydroascorbate reductase (DHAR) provides synergistic protection. These studies reported reduced reactive oxygen species accumulation, decreased membrane damage, and enhanced stress tolerance compared with plants overexpressing a single gene. [14].

IV.II Promoter choice and expression control

The choice of promoter used to drive transgene expression plays an extremely important role in determining antioxidant enzyme levels within the plant system. A widely used promoter in plant genetic engineering is the CaMV 35S (Cauliflower mosaic virus 35S) constitutive promoter. This promoter drives continuous expression of the introduced gene regardless of environmental conditions. While such constitutive expression ensures stable enzyme production, it may place unnecessary metabolic burden on the plant under non-stress conditions. Persistent overexpression of antioxidant enzymes can disrupt normal redox homeostasis and divert cellular resources away from growth and development.

Stress-inducible promoters, on the other hand, offer a more regulated and context-dependent approach. For example, the SWPA2 peroxidase promoter, characterized by Young Pyo Lee et al. (2007), is activated specifically under oxidative stress conditions. Such promoters initiate antioxidant enzyme production only when ROS levels rise, thereby maintaining physiological balance during normal growth and avoiding any metabolic costs. Plants engineered with stress-inducible promoter systems have demonstrated improved oxidative stress tolerance without the growth penalties often associated with constitutive overexpression strategies. [14].

IV.III Metabolic balance and endogenous enzyme variability

It is difficult to predict the results of metabolic engineering as the activities of branch-point enzymes like lycopene β -cyclase and ϵ -cyclase differ greatly between species. Endogenous gene regulation can also be interrupted by introducing a transgene. For example, it has been demonstrated that CRTI expression amplifies and enhances endogenous lycopene β -cyclase, rerouting metabolic flux in unpredictable ways. Controlling flux distribution and getting hold of the desired metabolite profile become more difficult by such interactions. Improving one antioxidant metabolite shouldn't interfere with the metabolism of the entire plant. The presence of a single

product can disrupt hormone pathways, which can cause adversities like feedback inhibition. Because of the excessive reduction of geranylgeranyl diphosphate pool, even slight pathway interference and disturbance can result in certain phenotypes such as dwarfism observed in tomatoes when PSY is expressed indefinitely. This truly tells us the importance and necessity of carefully balancing pathways and selecting promoters. [15]. Improving one antioxidant pathway may interfere with other cellular functions. For example, the FeSOD1 transgene changed the ultrastructure of chloroplasts and produced "enlarged plastoglobuli and increased starch grains in guard-cell plastids," suggesting that high SOD activity may change the biochemistry of plastids. Similarly, stacking of multiple enzymes could lead to unwanted metabolic or epigenetic imbalances. [4]

IV.VI Unintended effects on photosynthesis

Even though we know that overexpression of γ -tocopherol methyltransferase significantly increases tocopherol and phenolic antioxidants, its effects on photosynthetic performance are still not clear. Accumulation of phenolic compounds and tocopherols might mainly protect membrane lipids and thylakoid structures without directly affecting the rate and speed of its photochemistry. [3]. In addition to this, when multiple antioxidant genes like SOD, APX, DHAR, GR are co-expressed or stacked, complex interaction may arise that affect stromal redox status, plastid's NADPH needs and the regeneration capacity of the AsA-GSH pathway. The impacts of single or combined antioxidant transgenes on photosynthesis are not well studied.

IV.V Phenotypic variability and gene-dosage effects

Antioxidant engineering often shows non-linear responses to gene dosage, where both low and high expression can be harmful. Such an imbalance seen can suggest that ROS scavenging pathways function in a narrow 'optimal range.' When activity falls below threshold, oxidative damage occurs. However, if it exceeds the threshold, activity is shown to have diminishing benefits because of limitations in downstream detoxification, such as restricted capacity of APX and CAT to handle the resulting H_2O_2 . Such results stress on the importance of carefully controlling transgene expression levels. Antioxidant pathways are closely related or interconnected and the plant's traits depend not only on the presence of a transgene but also the rate or level at which it is expressed compared to other elements of the ROS-scavenging system. Because of this, gene-dosage effects should be taken into consideration when planning strategies to engineer transgenic plants that can sustain in stressful environments, particularly for multi-gene stacking or constant overexpression methods. [1].

V. FUTURE PROSPECTS & CONCLUSION

The bioengineering of enhanced antioxidant systems in transgenic plants represents a promising strategy to improve tolerance against diverse abiotic stresses, including salinity, cold, heavy metals, and UV radiation. Advances in plant genetic engineering have enabled targeted manipulation of

enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant pathways through approaches such as overexpression of individual antioxidant genes, organelle-targeted expression, multi-gene stacking, and metabolic engineering of antioxidant metabolites. These strategies have consistently demonstrated improved reactive oxygen species detoxification, reduced oxidative damage, stabilized photosynthetic machinery, and enhanced plant growth under stress conditions.

However, the effectiveness of antioxidant engineering depends on maintaining cellular redox balance and metabolic homeostasis. Challenges such as pathway interactions, gene-dosage effects, promoter selection, metabolic trade-offs, and unintended physiological changes highlight the complexity of ROS regulation in plants. These limitations emphasize the need for precise control of transgene expression and better understanding of interconnected metabolic networks.

Future research should focus on integrative approaches, including organelle-specific targeting, stress-inducible promoters, and coordinated expression of multiple antioxidant pathways to optimize stress tolerance while minimizing metabolic burden. With continued advancements in molecular tools and systems-level understanding, antioxidant bioengineering holds significant potential for developing resilient crop varieties capable of sustaining productivity under changing environmental conditions, thereby contributing to global food security and sustainable agriculture.

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